

THE GENESIS OF PETROLEUM SUBSIDY POLICY, AND THE CHALLENGE OF PETROL SHORTAGES IN NIGERIA.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20324656>

Abstract: Opinions have differed sharply in Nigeria on the continued existence of fuel subsidy. The opponents of the government-planned removal of fuel subsidy argue that the existence of fuel subsidy is a fallacy. On the other hand, the proponents opine that the existence of fuel subsidy is a fact. The objective of this study is to empirically examine these claims and counterclaims. This article traced the genesis of the subsidy regime in Nigeria. The author utilized both primary and secondary data to historicize the phenomenon of subsidy policy in Nigeria's downstream stream sector. Primary data was generated through interviews with relevant stakeholders in the petroleum industry in Nigeria. On the other hand, the secondary sources were obtained at the NNPC library and the University of Exeter Library.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy, Petrol Shortages, Downstream Sector, Reform.

Introduction

The practice of subsidizing energy, including petroleum products, is widely practiced. A study by the International Energy Agency (IEA) covering 20 non-OECD states affirmed this position when it noted that as much as \$220 billion was spent on fuel subsidies in the year 2005.⁶²⁶ Two years later, the amount had almost doubled, as it moved to about \$350 billion among the same number of countries and regions.⁶²⁷ Arguably, the figures may be much more when compared to the cost of fuel subsidy in oil-producing countries such as Nigeria, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Angola, among others. The chapter sets out to attempt the second research question "What is the impact of the implementation of the subsidy regime on the availability of petroleum products in Nigeria?" It looks at the implementation of subsidy in Nigeria and how it impedes the adequate supply of petrol within the domestic economy.

Fundamentally, the chapter argues that the implementation of subsidies on petroleum products serves special interests and constrains local supply. To achieve this objective, the chapter is further divided into four sub-themes, including the genesis of petrol subsidy, the battle to withdraw subsidy on petrol, the position of stakeholders in the subsidy debate, and corruption in the administration of subsidy policy. Under the first subtheme, the chapter argues that the history of subsidy precedes the 1990s, which is believed to be the starting point of subsidy in Nigeria. The chapter traced the origin of the policy to the second half of the 1960s when refining of petrol began in the Nigerian downstream sector.

The Genesis of Petrol Subsidy

Following the discovery and production of petroleum in the late 1950s, the dominant International Oil Company in Nigeria (Shell), along with British Petroleum (BP) and the Nigerian government, entered into a joint venture to establish Nigeria's first oil refinery.¹ The composition of Nigeria's federal government in the First Republic (1963-1966) meant that the key decisions on fiscal spending require the cooperation of the three regional governments – the Northern, Western, and Eastern governments.² It was these agreements that led to the establishment of the first refinery in Port Harcourt in 1965. The first indigenous petroleum scientists noted that Shell-BP was required to “supply the feed for it at the technical production cost of the crude.”³ As an incentive for supplying the feed, the agreement exempted Shell-BP from payment of royalties.⁴ Based on the currency exchange rate at the time, this implies that one barrel of crude fed into the refinery cost less than \$1 US. Marinho, who was privy to the negotiation, noted that such an arrangement meant that the refinery merely processed the crude at a “free and fair arm's length fee.”⁵

The economic thinking that drove the signing of the agreement was premised on the need to allow the investors in the refinery to make a reasonable return on their investments in line with the principle of ‘stand-alone investment.’ The adoption of the stand-alone principle allowed stakeholders to appraise the cost of their investment and the benefits therein.⁶ By the early 1970s, petrol marketers came into the business. They were expected to procure the crude and “obtain products at a fee.”⁷ This arrangement also allows the marketers to obtain the products “according to a slate of products obtainable from a designated barrel of crude.”⁸ While many sources, including key policy statements in contemporary Nigeria, have always made the claim of the origin of petrol subsidy to the early 1990s, the reality is that the incentives and discounts that saw the establishment of a joint venture refinery in Port Harcourt laid within it the genesis of petrol subsidy in Nigeria. This has been unambiguously noted by an insider privy to the development of subsidy policy in the following words:

“That initial, inconsequential economic concession was the genesis of the ‘petroleum products’ price subsidy that ultimately grew into an avalanche that has been very serious threats to the economic well-being and development of the nation: an albatross round the nation's neck that is threatening to choke sustainable economic life out of it.”⁹

¹ Frynas, Jędrzej George, Matthias P. Beck, and Kamel Mellahi. "Maintaining corporate dominance after decolonization: the 'first mover' advantages of Shell-BP in Nigeria." *Review of African Political Economy* 27, no. 85 (2000): 407-425.

² Diamond, Larry. *Class, ethnicity, and democracy in Nigeria: The failure of the first republic*. Syracuse University Press, 1988.

³ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria's Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited. P. 289.

⁴ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria's Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 292.

⁵ Marinho F. R. A. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, July, 2020.

⁶ Federal Government of Nigeria, Annual Report of the Petroleum Division of the Federal Ministry of Mines and Power, 1968–9, Ministry of Information, Abuja. 1970. p. 8.

⁷ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria's Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 290.

⁸ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria's Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 293.

⁹ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria's Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 293.

Given the huge incentives that accrued to the participating stakeholders, it was expected that such a move would encourage them to invest more in infrastructure, which was still not enough to cover the gap in the domestic supply of petrol to the burgeoning Nigerian economy of the 1970s.¹⁰ Some interviewees have attributed the various cases of product shortages witnessed during the 1970s to the “unwillingness of the benefitting private stakeholders”¹¹ who were making huge gains from the joint venture agreement. A well-placed bureaucrat supported the claim that private investors like Shell-BP were reluctant to build infrastructure in the downstream sector, leading to product shortages and economic hardship:

“A petroleum products’ shortage crisis built up...largely because the marketers were unwilling to make capital commitments, and cautiously held back from investing in the expansion of infrastructures that were so vitally crucial for coping with the exponentially growing products’ demand.”¹²

Realizing the reluctance of the private actor to build infrastructure in the oil industry, the Nigerian government capitalized on the intervention of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) to increase its shares within the entire industry, including the refining sector.¹³ As part of the precondition to join OPEC, Nigeria was expected to exercise dominant control over its oil industry as was the case with other member states.¹⁴ Consequently, the Nigerian government increased its shareholding to 60 percent and the refinery was registered as Nigeria Petroleum Refining Company (NPRC) in the early 1970s.¹⁵ However, the Joint Venture agreement remained in place and the composition of the management was still led by private hands. Considering the popularity of the ideology of socialism in the 1970s, critics saw no rationale for the continued control and management of the private sector in an industry that was 60 percent owned by the Nigerian government.¹⁶ Again, Nigeria’s policy of encouraging indigenous enterprises (indigenization policy), which was integrated into the National Development Plans, acknowledged the “fact that the country needed to take a quantum leap in the provision of the infrastructure needed to cope with the debilitating shortages standing the way of projected economic development.”¹⁷

By the second half of the 1970s, it had become completely ‘Nigerianized’ as the remaining 40 percent shares hitherto held by International Oil Companies were acquired by the socialist-leaning federal military government of General Olusegun Obasanjo. In specific terms, the complete takeover was actualized a year after the

¹⁰ Turner, Terisa Elaine. "Government and Oil in Nigeria: A Study of the Making and Implementation of Petroleum Policy." PhD diss., London School of Economics and Political Science (University of London), 1977.

¹¹ Abdulrazak, Ademola. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 12th July, 2020.

¹² Marihno, F.R.A. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 13th July, 2020.

¹³ At the end of the 1960s, the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) has mandated member countries to retain significant control of the oil industry in both the upstream and downstream sectors.

¹⁴ Nigeria was expected to comply with this condition before it can join the cartel.

¹⁵ NPRC Company reports 1972

¹⁶ Genova, Ann. "Nigeria's nationalization of British Petroleum." *The International Journal of African Historical Studies* 43, no. 1 (2010): 115-136.

¹⁷ Ogbuagu, Chibuzo SA. "The Nigerian indigenization policy: Nationalism or pragmatism?." *African Affairs* (1983): 241-266.

establishment of the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), the successor agency to the Nigeria National Oil Company (NNOC). With this development, it would appear that the subsidy policy was taking fuller shape as the government struggled to gain greater control of the oil industry and the downstream sector in particular. An insider who objected to the move but was unable to convince the authority to take an alternate route wrote that “When the Warri refinery came on stream, crude was fed to it at a royalty cost. That implied a continuation of the Government’s policy of providing products at a subsidy.”¹⁸

Further corroborating the viewpoint above, a participant who retired after serving the NNPC for three decades confirmed the government’s policy of paying for royalty cost:

“I was responsible for monitoring compliance with the policy of subsidizing the cost of production. We ensure that the relevant stakeholders within the downstream sector complied with the requirement in order to reduce the cost of petrol products. It was costly but necessary to reduce the burden of having to buy petrol at high prices.”¹⁹

The brief history provided above shows the evolution of petrol subsidy stretching back to the beginning of petrol refining in Nigeria. This narrative has helped to deepen the historicity of the policy, which has clearly become problematic to the government and ‘informed’ citizens in recent times. But even before 1978, when the government took the bold step to acquire the remaining 40 percent, completing its total ownership of the refineries, the Yakubu Gowon regime initiated a special fund known as the Petroleum Equalization Fund (PEF) through “Decree No. 9 of 1975.”²⁰ Therefore, the following further explains the evolution of a full-scale subsidy policy in Nigeria’s downstream sector from the mid-1970s.

Petroleum Equalization Fund (PEF)

The PEF was set up by the military regime of General Yakubu Gowon through the promulgation of Decree No. 9 of 1975 with the mandate to curb the challenge of disparity in the price of petrol across the different geopolitical regions in Nigeria.²¹ The establishment act stated the main objective of the fund in the following words:

“...to be applied for the reimbursement of petroleum marketing companies for any losses suffered by them arising from the sale of petroleum products at uniform prices throughout Nigeria.”²²

This implies that freight charges incurred in the course of transporting petroleum products from the refineries to the filling stations located in any part of the country would be shouldered by the government through the fund. To General Gowon and the military elites at the time, PEF would not only resolve the challenge of price variation based on the cost of transporting refined products, it would also serve as the basis on which uneven economic development could be tackled and minimized. Yakubu Gowon unreservedly stated this point of view at the launch of the programme in the following words:

¹⁸ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria’s Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 296.

¹⁹ Marinho, F.R.A Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 12th July, 2020.

²⁰ The decree was later amended by Decree No. 32 of 1989 during the IBB regime (1985-1993). PEF Financial Statements, 1982, p.5.

²¹ PEF Financial Statements, 1982, p.5.

²² Section 2 Petroleum Equalization Fund (Management Board etc) Decree Number 9 of 1975.

“Differentials in prices of petroleum products should not hamper the dispersal of industries throughout the country. Also, industries will no longer use it as an excuse for not wishing to establish far afield, nor will it impede the speedy implementation of various development projects of the state governments.”²³

Perhaps another angle to look at the issue that led to the implementation of the equalization fund was the overwhelming influence of the Northern Oligarchy, which masterminded the coup that brought Gowon to power.²⁴ Arguably, the *Kaduna Mafia*,²⁵ as they were called, exercised dominant control of the Nigerian state in the same way Mearsheimer and Walt talked about the “Israel lobby,”²⁶ albeit not without resistance from other regions of the country, especially the minority groups in the Middle Belt and Niger Delta regions, who regard themselves as the hosts of Nigeria’s oil treasure.⁶⁵⁸ This is not surprising in view of the position of literature on the rentier state, particularly the studies by Shambayati on the influential powers of “special interest groups”²⁷ who struggle to control oil wealth. While Shambayati’s account is focused on Turkey and Iran, Nigeria’s power elites, especially of Northern extraction, have also been noted to be the nucleus of state power.²⁸ The case in Nigeria is presumably worse because of the structure of power that has been established during the period of colonization.

At the time, it is difficult to ascertain the reality of power relations among the different regions and interest groups, considering the heavy-weight of politics involved. Whatever is the structure of power in the Nigeria oil industry, the subsidy policy has further created serious damage to the distribution of petrol as marketers continue to divert petrol to neighbouring markets for higher prices as discussed in chapter five and also engaged in false claims without delivering the products.

With the coming into force of PEF in 1975, many had hoped not only that the challenge of price disparity would be resolved but that the Fund would help to also mitigate the problem of severe scarcity, especially in places that have no refineries. One instance of this positive expectation can be seen from the appreciation message from some traditional rulers in the Northern part of the country who thanked the initiative, published in the 15th September issue of *Daily Nigerian*.²⁹ Disappointingly, a few months after the launch of the subsidy scheme, the challenge of petrol scarcity and price disparity lingered. A bureaucrat who has put in at least two decades of service with the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation observed the scary nature of petrol shortages after the launch of the PEF:

²³ Olakunle, Dele. Gowon hints at subsidy policy” *Daily Times* 13 June, 1975. pp. 1 and 31.

²⁴ Collins, Paul, M. Dixon, and Gavin Williams. “Nigeria: capitalism and the coup.” *Review of African Political Economy* 4 (1975): 95-98.

²⁵ Ogunjimi, Bayo. “The Herd Instinct and Class Literature in Nigeria Today.” *African Issues* 20, no. 2 (1992): 12-16.

²⁶ Mearsheimer, John J., and Stephen M. Walt. *The Israel lobby and US foreign policy*. (2006).

²⁷ Shambayati, Hootan. “The rentier state, interest groups, and the paradox of autonomy: state and business in Turkey and Iran.” *Comparative Politics* (1994): 307-331.

²⁸ The Middle Belt region comprises of states in North Central Nigeria where over 100 ethnic groups settled and have a significant number of its people in the armed forces of the country. While the Niger Delta region is arguably the wealthiest region hosting the oil wealth of the country

²⁹ Yahaya, Abdul. “Letter of Appreciation” *Daily Nigerian* 15 September 1975. P. 14.

“For those old enough to remember, the fuel scarcity of the 1970s was scarier than what we experienced in the 90s and the early years of the 21st Century. At the time, fuel demands had so outstripped supply that it was rationed based on the ‘odd’ and ‘even’ number plates of vehicles in Lagos.”³⁰

Truly, there were reports of severe shortages in 1975, culminating in the setting up of a “judicial commission of inquiry”⁶⁶⁴ to look into the problem. The mere fact that petrol price disparity persisted after the Fund was established means that it was either underfunded or it failed in the discharge of its primary duty. The objective to resolve price disparity across the vast expanse of the Nigerian state and to ensure uniform prices for petroleum products may be good but the implementation have had serious challenges as noted by one insider:

“The abundant evidence of disappearing long haul tankers that were entitled to collect bridging subsidies was clear proof that goods were being put into the pockets of ill-intentioned marketers who were concerned with across the border than supplying products to areas in Nigeria that were suffering from acute shortages of products.”³¹

The issue of petrol diversion to neighbouring countries for higher gains by oil marketers has been extensively discussed in chapter five. As has been noted, the establishment of PEF was largely informed by political rather than economic consideration. Also, the implementation in the initial years, just as in the present was challenged by unpatriotic elements who took advantage of the porous borders to engage in smuggling of petrol to neighbouring states. Against available knowledge, an attempt has been made to establish the fact that the policy of providing subsidy on petrol products can be traced back in the early period of refining petrol in Nigeria. Most importantly, it is pertinent to note that its implementation is challenged by sharp practices resulting in petrol shortages and continued price disparity across the various regions in Nigeria. Following this observation, an explanation of the various attempts to withdraw subsidies across different political regimes/administrations is made below.

The Petroleum Support Fund (PSF)

The PSF was initiated by Olusegun Obasanjo’s administration on the 46th anniversary of Nigeria in 2005.³² The main objective of the PSF is to cushion the effect of “volatility in the international price for crude and refined petroleum products on the domestic pump prices of petroleum products.”³³ Preparatory to its take off in January 2006, the directive on the operations of the fund was drafted by the stakeholders in the Nigerian oil industry, led by the Petroleum Product Pricing and Regulatory Agency (PPPRA).³⁴ In tandem with Nigeria’s federal system, the fund is derived from a contribution to be made by the three tiers of government, namely, the federal, state, and local governments.³⁵ By this arrangement, the Federal government is mandated to cater for 50 percent of the

³⁰ Maradan, Muyiwa. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 13th July, 2020.

³¹ Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria’s Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 296

³² Marinho, F. R. A. *Nigeria’s Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. P. 297.

³³ Petroleum Products Pricing Regulatory Agency. “Report on the Administration of the Petroleum Support Fund (PSF) January, 2006 - July 2008.

³⁴ Ibid., p. 1.

³⁵ In essence, its mandate is derived from the PPPRA Act No. 8 of May 2003.

fund while the states and local governments are to contribute 25 percent each. The management of the fund is done by the Federal Ministry of Finance, through the recommendation of PPPRA. On its part, the PPPRA would rely on reports of the quantity and quality of the delivered petroleum products from other agencies such as the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR). To ensure this is done according to the plan, the implementation guideline requires the service of an auditor, preferably appointed by the government.³⁶

Essentially, the fund was designed to ease the pressure on marketers who need finances to carry out the business of importing refined products. The desire to access funds by marketers led to the establishment of two Sovereign Debt Instruments (SDIs). These include the Sovereign Debt Statement (SDS) and the Sovereign Debt Note (SDN). By design, these two SDIs are meant to serve as promissory notes meant to assure oil marketers of prompt payment of subsidy benefits. From the draft, the payment of liabilities of oil marketers is not to exceed “45 days once verified.”³⁷ By this arrangement, oil marketers are to be reimbursed through a process called “cost recovery,” where the landing cost exceeds the regulated price at the depot. When the landing cost exceeds the regulated price, the payments of the gap to oil marketers are known as “under recovery.” On the contrary, where the cost of landing is lower than the regulated price, oil marketers are required to pay excess to the fund through a process known as “over recovery.”

Conclusion

In conclusion, the state-owned corporation, the NNPC, appears to be the most significant and influential oil marketer in the downstream sector of Nigeria’s oil industry. But as a result of the lack of turnaround maintenance of its four refineries, it has resorted to the importation of refined petroleum products, including petrol. According to available statistics, the refineries have rarely reached a combined average of 40 percent of capacity over the last two decades. This is despite the huge sum of money, mostly in “hundreds of US dollars, allocated for turnaround maintenance.”³⁸ Thus, one can argue that the birth of the subsidy policy is directly linked to the failure of refineries to meet local demand, leading to import dependence. Essentially, the problem in the downstream sector, particularly the implementation of the subsidy policy, is challenged by corruption. The following subthemes are dedicated to the explanation of this factor.

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³⁶ PPPRA Act No. 8 of May 2003.

³⁷ Bayo, Ogundipe. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 20th July, 2020.

³⁸ Munaghai, Usolo. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 14th July, 2020.

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